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Glossary

DT	Digital Twin	VI	Virtual Instrument
g	Model describing the virtual entity	V2P	Virtual to Physical
GUM	Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement	X	Measurement data
IF	Influence Factor	Y	Measurand
ISO	International Organization for Standardization	Z	Influence factors and error sources considered in g
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission	θ	Hyperparameters of g
JCGM	Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology		
LPU	Law of Propagation of Uncertainty		
MC	Monte Carlo		
t	Time		
P2V	Physical to Virtual		
PoD	Propagation of Distribution		
VE	Virtual Experiment		

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Summary

This Good Practice Guide (GPG) was written as part of Activity 2.4.5 of the European Partnership on Metrology project “Trustworthy virtual experiments and digital twins” (ViDiT), which commenced on May 1st, 2023. The overall aim of this three-year project is to develop methods and tools that enable ensuring the reliability and trustworthiness of virtual experiments and digital twins in metrology. For further details about this project, please visit vidit.ptb.de.

This GPG has been developed as part of Work Package 2 (WP2) to support the effective evaluation of uncertainty in the Digital Twins (DTs) designed for advanced metrology applications. Building on the results and methodologies established in tasks A2.2.1 to A2.2.5, A2.3.1 to A2.3.5, and A2.4.1 to A2.4.4, this document has been prepared under the leadership of Politecnico di Torino (POLITO), in close collaboration with Università degli Studi di Padova (UNIPD), Laboratoire national de métrologie et d'essais (LNE), Université Sorbonne-Paris-Nord (USPN), GEOMNIA, TEKNIKER, IDEKO, VTT, Fundación para el Fomento de la Innovación Industrial (FFII), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Instituto Nacional de Tecnología Industrial (INTI), and TUBITAK.

This GPG summarizes and outlines methods to carry out the uncertainty evaluation for the DTs with a description of their application to the four complex measurement use cases: nanoindentation (POLITO, UNIPD), 3D robotic measurement (IDEKO, TEKNIKER, VTT), rotary table for primary angular measurements (LNE), and electrical measurement (UPM, FFII, INTI), addressed in the project. All these DTs include dynamic effects (such as thermal drift or vibrations); hence the model has to be updated according to the sensor data. In addition to providing practical guidance on the implementation of these uncertainty evaluation methods, the GPG presents a comparative analysis of their performance across the different DTs. This comparative evaluation is intended to support both technical decision-making and future developments in the field.

This guide is aimed at metrologists, scientists, and engineers who are familiar with the basic ideas of uncertainty evaluation. A reader who is familiar with the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM) and its supplements or who is familiar with the Monte Carlo sampling method for uncertainty evaluation will be able to understand, and hopefully benefit from, this guide.

Trustworthy virtual experiments and digital twins

Good practice guide on uncertainty evaluation for digital twins

Deliverable 2 of Work Package WP2 (WP2: Uncertainty evaluation for DTs)

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1 Introduction

The concept of Digital Twins (DTs) was introduced by Grieves and Vickers from NASA as a virtual representation of a physical object also containing digital information of such product (Grieves 2014, Grieves et al. 2017). The DT concept was developed in the context of product life-cycle management, and has since been applied in many fields: predictive maintenance (Errandonea et al 2020) and real-time control and monitoring of buildings and bridges for civil engineering (Yoon et al 2023), manufacturing technologies (Cimino et al 2019, Liu et al 2022, Zhang C et al 2023) and assembling (Pang J et al 2023, Zhang C et al 2023) and disassembling (Verna et al 2024) processes and related products (Jones et al 2020), workflow for factory logistics (Magnanini et al 2021, Mengke et al 2023), healthcare (Cellina et al 2023, Kononowicz et al 2109), energy applications for plants to optimize resource production efficiency (Fathy et al 2021, Ghenai C et al 2022, Kasper et al 2022), and smart cities to control and optimize traffic and resources within an integrated IT framework (Dani et al 2023, Deng et al 2021).

Subsequent definitions tailored the concept, according to the needs of various application contexts in technological industries and fields distinguished by high automation capabilities, as those previously mentioned specifying, as depicted in Figure 1, that a DT includes the following:

- A **physical entity**, representing the entity the DT models and controls embedded in a physical environment tasked to carry out certain physical process; and
- A **virtual entity**, fit in a virtual environment, i.e., the digital representation of the physical entity and its environment.

Figure 1. Conceptual workflow of a DT, establishing relationship between main parts: Physical and Virtual entities, and bi-directional twinning.

A further distinguishing element of a DT is the two-way twinning, i.e., the two-way automatic connection and data flow, between the physical and the virtual asset. In particular, it can be distinguished by a **physical-to-virtual** (P2V) connection, through which the physical entity is transferred to the virtual environment by means of sensors measuring relevant quantities to represent the current state of the entity, and a **virtual-to-physical** (V2P) connection aiming at controlling the physical entity and the physical process. The control is performed based on a decision-making engine embedded in the virtual environment. Specifically, the virtual process simulates and models the physical process based on the sensed and measured state of the physical entity and environment and predicts the next state of the system considering the task to carry out.

Accordingly, based on the predicted outcome, control strategies can be deployed, by

means of actuators through the V2P connection, to modify the state of the physical entity with the scope of optimizing the process and/or the outcome, i.e., preventing defects, out-of-control states, damages, etc. (Jones et al 2020). As a matter of fact, a DT cannot be considered as only data; rather, it shall include algorithms describing the asset's behaviour and deciding on actions to deploy in the process (Boschert et al, Errandonea et al 2020), while predicting the system's response to unexpected events, before they occur, and preventing faults, damages, and hazards (Errandonea et al 2020, Schleich et al 2017). Measurement, and in particular metrology, covers a pivotal role in DTs since it ensures accurate measurement (i.e., sensing) and deployment (i.e., actuation) throughout the twinning phases (Jones et al 2020).

Such a large adoption of DT technologies results in a massive literature, sometimes inorganic and providing manifold definitions for DTs (Liu M et al 2021). Recent literature reviews (Cimino et al 2019, Errandonea et al 2020, Liu M et al 2021, Jones et al 2021, VanDerHorn et al 2021) showed that, often, DTs are confounded with digital models, i.e., simulation or digital representations in which data flow manually from the physical to the virtual entity, thus being static, or with digital shadows, i.e., simulation models that are automatically updated to reflect the current state of the physical entity and environment, but with no automatic real-time control. The widespread interest in DTs has therefore led to the development of standards for the unambiguous definition of the concept. Specifically, **ISO 23247:2021** defines the DT as a

fit-for-purpose digital representation, i.e., data element representing a set of properties of an observable manufacturing element (OME), with synchronization between the element and its digital representation.

ISO 23247:2021 specifies an Internet of Things framework to build and deploy DTs in manufacturing technologies. In particular, while highlighting the main features, e.g., fidelity and granularity (i.e., the representation detail of the DT), ISO 23247:2021, although not including it in the definition, specifies, according to the literature, the main applications, i.e., detection of anomalies, achievement of objective by real-time correction, off-line analytics, and predictive maintenance, while relying on the update rate, defined on a task-specific base, and relying on the previous and current state of the OME to analyse the current condition or predict its future state.

Similarly, **ISO/IEC 30173:2023** defines the DT as digital representation, i.e.,

a digital entity representing either a set of properties or behaviors or both of one or more observable elements of a target entity, i.e., an entity providing a functional purpose in reality, with data connections that enable convergence between the physical and digital states at an appropriate rate of synchronization.

ISO/IEC 30173:2023 provides more general definitions of relevant and distinctive elements of the DT and its framework going beyond the manufacturing technology scope of ISO 23247:2021. Such generalization introduces the concept of a DT system as a system providing functionalities for the DT composed of inter-operating target entities, digital entities, data connections, and models, data and interfaces involved in the data connection process, and still includes, although not as a prominent feature, the control loop used to receive data from the target entity and issue back

a signal to modify its behaviour.

ISO standards particularly stress the difference between DTs and other typical enabling technologies of Industry 4.0. In particular, they point out that the two-way twinning and control loop is an essential feature of DTs, distinguishing them from Virtual Experiments (VEs), Virtual Instruments (VIs) and other simulation models, and that Internet of Things is an enabling technology of DTs, which on its turn is an enabling technology for cyber-physical systems (Hughes et al 2024, Maculotti et al 2024a). The twinning is realized by sensors (P2V) and actuators (V2P) whose metrology is of utmost relevance to establish traceability and guaranteed trustworthiness in the DT outcome. The standards introduce some performance metrics and terminology, e.g., accuracy and fidelity, and state the relevance of performance verification and validation, which are consistent with the literature.

ViDiT (www.vidit.ptb.de) project focused on methodologies to establish traceability of DTs and on methods to evaluate measurement uncertainties of developed DT, fit for both prediction and decision-making purposes. The project specifically focused on DT of measurement process and measurement instruments.

According to (Maculotti et al 2024a), a possible formalization of a DT is possible. Reminding that a DT is based on data (collected in the physical environment and fed to the virtual twin by the P2V twinning), it estimates and predicts by the virtual asset of the state of the physical entity, and if needed, it deploys control strategies through the V2P connection. Then, if needed, the model can be updated to match the control; henceforth, the related VE becomes time dependent, and as such, the virtual entity can be viewed as:

$$X = g(Y, \mathbf{Z}, t; \boldsymbol{\vartheta}) \quad (1.1),$$

where, X is the measurement data, simulated in a virtual environment, from a certain measuring instrument on Y , i.e. the measurand, which is the quantity of interest in a measurement and for which, ultimately, an uncertainty evaluation has to be performed. The values of the usually multivariate parameter \mathbf{Z} represent a variety of elements, e.g., physical quantities, i.e. influence factors (IFs), characteristics of the measurement instrument, error sources, whereas $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$ are the hyperparameters. In real measurements, the actual parameter \mathbf{Z} is unknown but fixed under repeated measurements.

Such framework is readily applicable to any other application, as more complex system, and manufacturing elements, e.g. production lines, production systems, plant, cities, etc. In such cases, Y is the actual state of the system, X measurements generated by such system state by relevant sensor.

Here, it is also worth noting that real measurements attempt estimating Y from X , most typically from realizations of X , i.e. x , by data analysis, i.e.

$$\hat{Y} = f(X, \mathbf{Z}, t; \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \quad (1.2).$$

Such measurand, or system state, estimation \hat{Y} is essential for decision making during the V2P twinning, for which uncertainty estimation is critical. Under most conditions, f is an identity. Under most general formulation f can depend on hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$, and, in the case of DT, liable of time-dependency, f is also a function of time t .

An example can be, for a Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM), the measurement (X) of a spherical surface of a priori unknown radius of a sphere, i.e. the measurand Y . A further example can be the position estimation of an articulated arm robot, where the actual position, i.e. the unknown system state Y , is estimated by a

composition of angular encoders measurements X .

1.1 Uncertainty Evaluation Methodology

Essentially, according to the previous discussion based on the literature and ISO standard definitions, a DT can be considered a simulation model that accurately replicates a physical system in a virtual environment and that includes automated dynamic updates of the virtual model according to the observed state of its real counterpart to achieve an as-automated-as-possible physical control of the latter. The four main parts of a DT are the physical entity, the virtual entity, and the P2V and the V2P twinning, enabling the bi-directional data flow and synchronization.

1.1.1 Influence factors

Figure 2 highlights the influence factor (IFs) of a DT, according to its main constitutive components.

Physical entity, i.e. the measurand, is affected by task-specific IFs due to the considered system and the relevant environment.

More general discussion can be provided, on the other hand, for other contributions.

Sensors measure data that are then fed into the Virtual entity, i.e. the associated VE, enabling the P2V twinning. Thus, the P2V twinning introduces sources of uncertainty in the DT due to the twinning rate, mostly systematic contributions related for example to aliasing, and due to sensors. These, in particular, contributes to *diagnostic* uncertainty (Karve et al 2020), due to traceability and metrological characteristics of the sensors.

Sensed data are then fed into the virtual entity. The related model introduces modelling, i.e. *epistemic*, errors due to selected IFs, the particular functional form of g , due to the fidelity; these contributions can be considered as essentially systematic errors. The virtual entity, i.e. the simulation, predicts the system response, i.e. estimate of X , that is \hat{X} , contributing with further random *prognostic* errors. By validating the virtual entity, it is possible to estimate some systematic errors, and if the validation is performed on calibrated measurands, it allows the estimation of accuracy.

Based on the predicted response \hat{X} , decision-making and physical entity control can be performed by actuators, thus implementing the V2P twinning. This phase introduces errors due to the twinning rate and due to actuators' metrological characteristics.

Last, the bi-directional feedback loop is critical. Ultimately, the control established by the DT can be viewed as a Kalman filter with uncertainty. Depending on the sensors available to perform the prediction of the system state, or of the measurement, critical consequences lead to uncertainty. Specifically, if only internal, i.e. *proprioceptive*, sensors are used, systematic errors and drifts cannot be detected, and uncertainty grows at each twinning loop. Conversely, if external, i.e. *exteroceptive*, sensors are also exploited, systematic errors and drifts can be corrected, while maintaining constant the measurement uncertainty (Sasiadek et al 2000, Lewis et al 2008).

Figure 2. Influence Factors of Digital Twins.

It is worth noting that by calibrating sensors and actuators, and by validating the virtual entity model by means of a calibrated measurand, it is possible to establish traceability of the DT, and to estimate prediction accuracy and uncertainty, as well as accuracy and uncertainty of the control (the latter only if exteroceptive sensors are used).

1.1.2 DT parametrization and statistical modelling

Once IFs and error sources \mathbf{Z} have been identified, the DT requires parametrization. This consists in establishing the model g . This can be done by several approaches. According to the literature, three main approaches are available: physics-based, data-driven, and hybrid approaches (Jones et al 2020, Karve et al 2020, Ritto et al 2021). The former solely relies on physical relationships to fix the functional form of g . This requires strict boundary condition and a thorough knowledge of the physics of the system. The dual approach is a data-driven solution, which selects the functional g , based on statistical goodness-of-fit measures. Machine learning typically fits within this category, e.g. by neural networks. Further, design of experiments can effectively and robustly support parameterization of the prediction based on \mathbf{Z} , i.e., IFs and error sources. The hybrid approach aims at coupling advantages of both aforementioned methodologies, e.g. by limiting the choice of mathematical models based on the physics of the system. Particularly relevant on the matter is physics-informed machine learning (Hao Z et al 2022).

Eventually, Eq. (1.1) and Eq. (1.2) can be rewritten highlighting the possible modelling uncertainty:

$$X = g(Y, \mathbf{Z}, t; \boldsymbol{\vartheta}) + E_X \quad (1.3)$$

$$\hat{Y} = f(X, \mathbf{Z}, t; \boldsymbol{\varphi}) + E_Y \quad (1.4),$$

Where E_X and E_Y are random error from the modelling, i.e. fitting error, representing the epistemic uncertainty contribution. Under the assumption of a correct fitting, $\mathbb{E}[E] = 0$, and $\text{Var}[E_X] = \sigma_X^2$, $\text{Var}[E_Y] = \sigma_Y^2$.

Selected IFs, error sources, and model parameters require statistical modelling to elicit the composition of related uncertainty contribution to eventually estimate the measurement uncertainty. Parametric or non-parametric approaches can be applied, as discussed in greater detail in Section 2. Here, it is sufficient to say that \mathbf{Z} and $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$ shall be associated with an expected value, i.e., $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{Z}]$ and $\mathbb{E}[\boldsymbol{\vartheta}]$, and a covariance, i.e., Σ_Z and $\Sigma_{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}$. Parametric modelling requires associating with \mathbf{Z} and $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$

relevant probability distribution (JCGM 100, JCGM 101).

1.1.3 Model simplification

Model simplification has computational, practical and conceptual advantages. Model can be simplified by removing IFs that are actually not statistically significant or that marginally contribute to the combined measurement uncertainty.

In the first case, several methods are available for feature selection, spanning from stepwise regression (McIntyre et al 1989) and principal component analysis (Dobson 1990). Further approaches can be available to create surrogate models, e.g. by Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) simplifying the modelling.

In the second case, uncertainty evaluation allows the identification and ranking of different IFs in terms of respective contribution to the overall combined uncertainty (JCGM GUM 100). Accordingly, the least impacting contributions can be considered to be removed from the uncertainty budget to alleviate the experimental effort required to statistically characterize the associated statistical distribution, i.e. the *statistical modelling* of §1.1.2.

1.2 Case Studies

The methodology for uncertainty evaluation of DT will be first generally presented in Section 2.

To demonstrate the practical implementation and effectiveness of the uncertainty evaluation methods described in this GPG, four representative and technically challenging measurement use cases have been selected. These use cases—nanoindentation, 3D robotic measurement, Rotary table for primary angular measurements, and electrical measurement—reflect a broad range of metrological scenarios and dynamic conditions relevant to the development and deployment of Digital Twins.

Each case study illustrates how the uncertainty evaluation methods can be applied in real-world contexts, highlighting the specific challenges associated with dynamic effects such as thermal drift, vibrations, and time-dependent behaviours. The selected use cases also showcase how sensor data integration and model updating are crucial for maintaining the accuracy and reliability of the DTs.

The following sections provide a detailed analysis of each use case, including the implementation of the uncertainty evaluation methods, the modelling strategies adopted, and the insights gained from their application. Here, in the next subsection, the use cases are here briefly described.

1.2.1 Nanoindentation

Nanoindentation indicates Instrumented Indentation Test (IIT) in the nano range. Nanoindentation is a very informative mechanical characterization technique, providing properties like hardness, modulus, and residual stress (Lucca et al 2010). IIT is a depth-sensing hardness test that consists of applying a force by an indenter on a sample to be characterized while measuring the applied force F and the indenter penetration depth h in the material during the whole test duration. Analysing the unloading portion of the indentation curve (IC) shown in Figure 3, i.e. $F(h)$, enables the evaluation of mechanical properties (Lucca et al 2010, ISO 14577-1:2015). Nanoindentation finds application in aerospace, automotive, semiconductor, nuclear, and biomedicine industries to optimize manufacturing processes, characterize microstructures, assess

mechanical properties of multi-layer materials decoupling the contribution of the coating and the substrates, and replace destructive tests for average bulk properties (Lucca et al 2010). Advanced measurement protocols extend from room to high-temperature testing and cover dynamic measurements (ISO 14577). These protocols are increasingly used for high-temperature applications (e.g. gas turbines, turbine blades, nuclear reactors, heat exchanger tubing, car electrification) and damping materials in automotive fields. Furthermore, the depth-sensing allows overcoming limits of conventional hardness tests and enables nanoscale and nanostructure characterization.

ISO 14577-2 requires periodic verification of the nanoindentation machine and test equipment. This is usually performed on candidate reference material (CRM), i.e., typically SiO₂. Similarly, nanoindentation can be used in production for quality assurance of mass-produced components, e.g. screen, wafer coatings.

A DT of nanoindentation aims at predicting the system response on a given material, e.g. the CMR or the mass-produced component, and managing the nanoindentation process enabling automatic measurement correction and system maintenance.

Figure 3. Indentation Curve (IC): applied Force (F) as a function of indenter penetration depth (h).

1.2.2 3D robotic measurements

Robotic optical scanning refers to a fully automated dimensional measurement system that combines a light-projection optical sensor with a robot arm to capture high-resolution 3D data from complex parts. The system is designed to perform non-contact measurements without any human intervention during the scanning process.

During operation, the robot precisely moves the optical sensor around the component, capturing its geometry from multiple angles. The system is capable of extracting dimensional features such as lengths, diameters, radii, and form or position deviations with high accuracy and repeatability.

The system performance is verified in accordance with ISO 10360-10, which defines procedures for testing the metrological behavior of non-contact coordinate measurement systems based on optical imaging. Regular verification and calibration procedures ensure that the system maintains its measurement capability over time.

One critical element to ensure traceability and control of measurement uncertainty is the calibration of the sensor's position with respect to the robot's end-effector. This calibration step enables accurate transformation of the measured data into the global coordinate frame.

The DT is composed of a physical entity (robot, sensor, calibration artefacts, and measured part) and a virtual counterpart that simulates the scanning and measurement process. The Physical-to-Virtual (P2V) connection is established through sensors collecting joint angles, and optical data, feeding them into the virtual entity. The virtual model predicts the measurement output and uncertainty budget considering influence factors such as, robot repeatability, sensor and robot calibration parameters, and part scanning behaviour.

The Virtual-to-Physical (V2P) twinning enables control feedback loops where the DT suggests corrections to compensate for identified drifts or deviations, either by modifying robot trajectories or adjusting the sensor acquisition parameters. Measurement uncertainty is evaluated in compliance with the JCGM:GUM framework.

Uncertainty sources are categorized as:

- Sensor-related: resolution, calibration error, and noise characteristics.
- Robot-related: repeatability, backlash, path planning accuracy.
- Model-related: fitting errors, simplifications, surrogate modelling (e.g. Gaussian Process Regression for high-speed uncertainty estimation).

Parametric and non-parametric models are used to quantify and propagate uncertainties through the DT. Statistical modelling is applied to input distributions, including hyperparameters and influence factors, to estimate the combined measurement uncertainty. The DT implementation also enables the separation of systematic and random error contributions, and supports traceability by validating predicted measurements against calibrated reference parts.

Ultimately, the DT of 3D robotic measurement systems enhances quality control workflows by ensuring:

- Real-time uncertainty prediction per measurement task,
- Autonomous error correction through control feedback,
- Continuous system performance monitoring,
- Traceability through sensor and model calibration,
- Scalable integration in production environments.

This robotic scanning system finds application in a wide range of industrial sectors, including:

- **Aerospace**, for the inspection of structural parts and complex geometries.
- **Welded and machined assemblies**, where large components must be verified efficiently.
- **Heavy equipment and yellow goods**, where robust, fast inspection is required on large-scale parts.
- **Advanced manufacturing**, for quality control and digital validation of prototypes and production parts.

This system and the methodology provides several advantages:

- Fully automated operation with no user influence on measurement results.
- Fast and accurate non-contact inspection of complex surfaces.

- Integration into production environments for in-line or near-line quality assurance.
- Reduction of human error and improved repeatability.
- Capability to inspect fragile or difficult-to-fixture parts.

1.2.3 Rotary table for primary angular measurements

As part of the national effort to strengthen angular metrology capabilities, the French Bureau National de Métrologie (BNM) and the Laboratoire National d'Essais (LNE) launched the development of a high-precision rotary table intended to serve as the national angular reference standard. This project was carried out in collaboration with the CRMAO laboratory at ENSAM Lille, with the objective of producing a continuously rotating system with extremely high angular accuracy and long-term stability (Figure 4).

Figure 4. LNE reference rotary table.

The system targets an expanded uncertainty of less than ± 0.1 arcseconds. The developed system addresses two main objectives:

- Provide a continuous angular reference for calibrating angle standards such as polygons and optical encoders, with reinforced traceability to the SI unit of angle.
- Achieve a controlled and highly accurate rotational motion, enabling the precise evaluation of angular measurement instruments and serving as a calibration basis for industrial applications.

1.2.4 Electrical measurements

➤ Sheath currents in high voltage cable systems

For the DT developed by UPM-FFII the model implemented is based on the physical study of high voltage (HV) insulated power cable systems using differential equations.

The expected fidelity of the model has been achieved considering, in the design process, the following three elements:

- The measured variables to be incorporated in the DT and the accuracy of their values.
- The cable system variables to be incorporated in the DT and the accuracy of their values.
- The calculation methods considered, and the possible approximations required.

The DT developed is focused on the estimation of the cable systems behaviour over time, concerning mainly the sheath currents estimation.

The interest of using this kind of system, is that already in the operating grids, in the design or commissioning phase, the process can be characterized without the need to perform complex and costly on-site measurements.

With this DT application there are no real-time or time-lapse interactions with cable systems in operation. The only interaction between a real cable system and the DT occurs when a defect or fault is detected with the DT, and corrective actions are established in the real physical system. In these cases, the predictable changes and possible improvements can be known simulating the modified cable system in the DT beforehand. Thus, the parameter twinning rate does not require special attention in this application.

The model fidelity is checked or validated by evaluating the deviation obtained between the measured data in a real cable system and the calculated data with the DT. In this regard, the most important and reference value will be the induced sheath currents.

In the DT developed by UPM-FFII, some parameters that describe the physical system are directly measured from a real cable system, or obtained from the physical characteristics of the assets and elements involved.

The V2P connection is focused on predicting the behaviour of the cable systems under study, and to improve the maintenance tasks of electrical utilities, by specifying the corrective actions to be undertaken (Jones et al 2020, Thelen et al 2023b, Zhou et al 2019, Qi et al 2018, Kochunas et al 2021).

➤ **Internal Arc Test (IAT)**

For the DT to be developed by INTI on short circuit withstand tests, also called Internal Arc Test (IAT) of a medium voltage electrical cell, the aim is to improve this standardized test controlling the electrical power used as input in the physical environment and reducing the cost of implementing several experimental tests on different compartments of the same metal-enclosed switchgear. Also, the result from its digital counterpart will be used to extrapolate the test for higher voltage configurations.

With this objective in mind, we acknowledge three input groups and their uncertainty to be considered for the P2V connection to simulate properly the physical system:

- Electric measurements, arc voltage, and current.
- Metal-enclosed switchgear dimensions.
- Other physical parameters such as density, thermal conductivity, heat capacity, etc.

Our biggest challenge is how to implement these standards related to the experimental test in the virtual environment. Most requirements and constraints for the measurement process come from the “Common specifications for high-voltage switchgear and controlgear standards”, and “High-voltage switchgear and controlgear – Part 200: AC metal-enclosed switchgear and controlgear for rated voltages above 1kV and up to and including 52 kV”. In these standards, the definitions, ratings, and criteria to pass the different type tests are defined. In particular, in the IAT type test an electric arc is created inside of a compartment, and the heat produced increases the pressure inside the volume. When the pressure reaches a certain value, a pressure valve or rupture disk opens and releases the pressurized gas, as seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Representation of internal arc and the expected flow after overpressure has been reached.

The objective is to verify the integrity of the enclosure related to the maximum pressure and temperature inside the volume. The physical model to be simulated with the Finite Difference Method (FDM) and Finite Volume Method (FVM) is taken from “Tools for the simulation of the internal arc in transmission and distribution switchgear”, and “Internal arc fault simulation using CFD to predict behaviour in switchgear”. This model includes mass, momentum, and energy conservation equations, and the ideal gas law as the state equation for the gas, air or SF₆, inside the compartment. The simulation helps to determine the temperature and pressure inside the switchgear and from this results the integrity of the enclosure can be analysed.

All sensors involved in the physical asset measurement process (voltage, current, temperature and pressure) will be calibrated according to “ISO/IEC 17025 standard” to assure traceability for those measurements and provide the input data for the uncertainty calculation.

➤ Quantum Voltage Standard (QVS)

The objective of this digital twin is to optimize the configuration parameters of the physical system of the Quantum Voltage Standard to reduce the setup and measurement time and optimize the transference of the SI voltage unit, the volt, to secondary standards.

The Physical-to-Virtual (P2V) connection is determined by measurements on the physical system that feeds the data-driven model. This model utilizes Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict the configuration parameters that will serve as control signals in the Virtual-to-Physical (V2P) connection. Figure 6 depicts these concepts.

Quantum Voltage Standard Digital Twin

Figure 6. Representation of the Quantum Voltage Standard Digital Twin.

Josephson voltage standards allow the generation of both DC and AC signals, enabling electrical voltages to be directly linked to the reference constants established by the International System of Units (SI), according to:

$$V_J(t) = n(t)(h)/2ef \quad (1.5),$$

where $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ is a quantum number, f is a microwave frequency referred to an atomic clock, h is the Planck constant, and e is the elementary charge.

The Programmable Josephson Voltage Standard (PJVS) is a Josephson system that can be used as a superconducting multi-bit digital-to-analog converter (DAC). The PJVS produces stable DC voltages or time-stepwise approximated waveforms, whose accuracy is determined by well-defined constant voltage steps, given by Eq. (1.5). Figure 7 shows an example of an AC signal.

Figure 7. The red curve represents an ideal sine wave of 1 V peak-with a frequency of 62.5 Hz. The blue curve shows the PJVS stepwise approximated signal with $n = 20$ steps per period.

Therefore, the main parameters to be optimized are:

Generated Josephson voltage [VJ], microwave frequency [f] and power, array critical current [Ic], helium level or cryocooler settings, synthesized signal frequency, and the number of steps per period [n].

We will evaluate accuracy, repeatability, and sensitivity according to the measurement system.

For the QVS, fidelity is represented by the measuring voltage accuracy of the theoretical Josephson voltage. The twinning rate depends on the measurement duration, as the model produces an output after every measurement.

2 Uncertainty Evaluation Methodology

This section highlights the available methods to evaluate the measurement uncertainty of the predicted measurement, i.e. $U(\hat{X})$, and of the estimated measurand, i.e. $U(\hat{Y})$.

2.1 GUM Compliant Approaches (LPU and PoD)

GUM compliant approaches are methods that are explicitly included in JCGM Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement and its annexes. Accordingly, two main approaches are available: the Law of Propagation of Uncertainty (LPU) and the Propagation of Distribution (PoD) method, also known as Monte Carlo (MC) method.

2.1.1 Law of Propagation of Uncertainty

A full detail of the approach is available in (JCGM GUM 100), here a brief summary of the methodology highlighting the specificities related to DT application is provided.

The application of LPU to the P2V twinning essentially requires estimating the uncertainty of the estimated measurements $U(\hat{X})$. According to the JCGM GUM 100, the $u_c(\hat{X})$, i.e. the combined uncertainty of the predicted measurements follows from the application of the LPU to Eq. (1.3):

$$u_c^2(\hat{X}) = \begin{bmatrix} J_{g(z,\vartheta)} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T \Sigma_X \begin{bmatrix} J_{g(z,\vartheta)} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\Sigma_X = \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_Z & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_\vartheta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{\hat{X}}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.2),$$

where $J_{g(z,\vartheta)}$ is the Jacobian of the estimated model g through the DT parametrization with respect to \mathbf{Z} and $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$. It is worth noting that catering for epistemic uncertainty by including $\sigma_{\hat{X}}^2$ allows estimating prediction intervals at a given confidence level P , thus estimating the $U(\hat{X})$:

$$U(\hat{X}) = t_{P,\nu_X} \cdot u_c(\hat{X}) \quad (2.3)$$

where t_{P,ν_X} is the quantile of a t-Student distribution identifying a bilateral risk of error of I kind equal to $1-P$, and ν_X are the effective degrees of freedom of the estimated measurements by Eq. (1.1), which can be obtained by the Welch-

Satterthwaite formula (JCGM GUM 100 – Annex G).

Subsequently, the V2P twinning requires estimating the system state by Eq. (1.4), via the data analysis model f . In the case this is not an identity (otherwise $\hat{X} = \hat{Y}$, and $U(\hat{X}) = U(\hat{Y})$), the LPU can be applied again:

$$u_c^2(\hat{Y}) = \begin{bmatrix} J_{f(X,Z,\varphi)} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T \Sigma_Y \begin{bmatrix} J_{f(X,Z,\varphi)} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.4)$$

$$\Sigma_Y = \begin{bmatrix} u_c^2(\hat{X}) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_Z & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Sigma_\varphi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_Y^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

$$U(\hat{Y}) = t_{p,\nu_Y} \cdot u_c(\hat{Y}) \quad (2.6).$$

It is worth pointing out that the statistical modelling of selected IFs and error sources, i.e. Z , is critical in defining the covariance matrix Σ_Z . In fact, each IF and error source, included in the DT parametrization. According to JCGM GUM 100, type A, i.e. statistical, or type B evaluation of standard uncertainty of Z can be performed. Details on such methods are available in JCGM GUM 100. Here, it is sufficient to remark that for variables for which type B evaluation is applied, all related covariance terms will not be evaluated and set to 0 in Σ_Z .

2.1.2 Propagation of Distribution

A full detail of the approach is available in (JCGM GUM 101), here a brief summary of the methodology highlighting the specificities related to DT application is provided.

The PoD is a simulative parametric method for uncertainty evaluation. It is also known as Monte Carlo (MC) method. It essentially consists in performing distributional hypotheses for each uncertainty contributor and then sample for such distributions. Figure 8 depicts the method. The approach may require extensive experimental effort to identify the most adequate probability distribution for each uncertainty contributor, and to estimate relevant parameters, e.g., $\overline{E}[Z]$ and $\overline{\Sigma}_Z$ for a normal distribution. Also, it is relevant to stress that in case some uncertainty contributors are correlated, correlation shall be modelled. This step might not be trivial and it can increase model complexity. Specifically, M sets of uncertainty contributors' realization will be sampled from underlying distributions, and then processed through the measurement model, which in the case of the P2V twinning will be the virtual entity model g , and from estimated outputs, confidence interval of the estimated response can be evaluated.

Some general best practices can be highlighted.

First, it is worth noting that the goodness of the result is highly dependent on the number M of Monte Carlo iterations. Specifically, given a confidence level of 100p%, it is recommended that $M \geq 10^4 \cdot 1/(1-p)$. For example, for a simple model and a 95% confidence level, $M = 10^6$ can often be expected to deliver a confidence interval for the output quantity such that this length is correct to one or two significant decimal digits.

Secondly, in case of asymmetric distribution of the response, JCGM GUM 101 recommends avoiding stating the uncertainty, i.e. the half-width of the supposedly symmetric confidence interval. Conversely, stating the whole

confidence interval shall be preferred. The confidence interval, in the case of asymmetric distribution of the response, shall be estimated as the minimum interval covering the set confidence level (clause D7 of JCGM GUM 101 provides computational and implementational details).

Figure 8. Simplified representation of Propagation of Distribution method for Uncertainty evaluation.

2.2 Other Simulative Approaches

Further simulative approaches are available for uncertainty evaluation. The most prominent of which being Bootstrapping (Efron 1979). Although this approach cannot be considered GUM-compliance, for it is not described in GUM and its annexes, it covers a significant role for uncertainty practitioners.

As discussed in §2.1.2, DoP is a parametric simulative approach which requires performing non-trivial distributional hypothesis on uncertainty contributors \mathbf{Z} . Conversely, Bootstrap allows a non-parametric simulation alternative. It consists of resampling an experimental dataset of K data in M samples (of size $m < K$), i.e. the bootstrap samples, and it allows evaluating M times the output whose uncertainty is of interest. Figure 9 depicts the method.

Figure 9. Simplified representation of Bootstrap method for Uncertainty evaluation

Advantages of Bootstrap are immediate. When PoD requires extensive preliminary experimental efforts to estimate parameters of distribution, and to estimate goodness of distributional hypothesis, Bootstrap can exploit the same data, directly, and with less statistical modelling effort from the practitioner. Specifically, Bootstrap method dispenses the user from performing nontrivial hypotheses and modelling if strong correlations between input quantities are present. Thus, Bootstrapping allows an approach which is user-agnostic.

However, Bootstrapping is strongly dependent on the goodness and numerosity of experimental data. Similar considerations to the previous paragraph can be required on the number of experimental observations to be collected to generate bootstrap sample, and on methods for managing possibly asymmetric response distributions.

2.3 Bayesian Approaches

Bayesian methods are the only methods, at the time of project writing that could be found in the literature (Karve et al 2020). Bayesian approaches are not GUM-compliant, but are most useful to manage time-evolving systems.

In particular, Monte Carlo Markov Chain (MCMC) allows greatest flexibility in managing the data. to estimate the posterior probability the measurement X in the P2V twinning, as:

$$p_{post}(X|y, z) = p_{likelihood}(y, z|x)p_{prior}(X) \quad (2.7).$$

The prior distribution might combine uncertainty contribution of sensors used to measure the quantity of interest, and the MCMC model allows to fuse heterogeneous information from different sensors.

Clearly, the approach allows for updating the model hyperparameters depending on time-varying conditions, i.e.

$$p_{post}(\vartheta|x) = p_{likelihood}(x|\vartheta)p_{prior}(\vartheta) \quad (2.8),$$

At a given twinning rate $1/\Delta t$, it is possible to observe the measurand, i.e. the system state, and update the model.

For DT applications, the interest lies in the fact that, in between twinning instants, the measurand, e.g. the system, state is actually unknown. Thus, formally, a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) is resorted to. More specifically, since a correlation between X and Z is present, an autoregressive model is considered.

$$p(x_t|x_{t-1}, y_t = k, z, \vartheta) = \mathcal{N}(x_t|W_k x_{t-1} + \mu_k, \Sigma_k) \quad (2.9),$$

In particular, in between twinning instants, it is possible to obtain inference on the future state, at a time instant $t + h$ ($h < \Delta t$) and more relevantly the future observation, i.e.

$$p(y_{t+h}|x_{1:t}) = \sum_{y_{t+1}} \sum_{y_t} p(y_{t+h}|y_{t+h-1})p(y_{t+h-1}|y_t)p(y_t|x_{1:t}) \quad (2.10)$$

$$p(x_{t+h}|x_{1:t}) = \sum_{y_{t+h}} p(x_{t+h}|y_{t+h})p(y_{t+h}|y_{1:t}) \quad (2.11).$$

Computational and formal details can be found elsewhere (Murphy 2012).

A typical graphical representation of HMM can be obtained by Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBN). A DBN structure is fixed, and the nodes represent the system state and arches the state change, to which a transition probability is associated (Murphy 2012).

The most recent review on the topic is (Thelen A et al 2023a) which highlights

the method suitable for both evaluating the uncertainty of the prediction and of state change. Some methodologies, e.g. Gaussian Process Regression and DBN, are natively Bayesian methods and allow evaluation of measurement uncertainty. These are typically used by practitioners for building DT. Other methods, e.g. Neural networks (NN), require ad-hoc methods for uncertainty evaluation (Thelen A et al 2023a, 2023b).

Here, it is relevant to stress that Bayesian methods are extremely useful when a finite set of working conditions (states) can be identified, or when a time evolution, i.e., a drift, is inherent in the system operation. Conversely, for applications aiming at a dicotomical modelling of the measuring instrument, i.e., in control and out-of-control, a Bayesian modelling find a much more limited relevance. Similarly, for instruments that are not supposed to drift, or whose drift is hard to model, and due to uncontrollable influence factors, e.g. wear, autoregressive models would require an extremely large number of experimental evidence for training.

3 Case Study 1: Nanoindentation

The DT of the nanoindentation system is obtained considering as input quantities the applied force F , platform related and calibrated parameters, i.e. the frame compliance C_f and the area shape function parameters a_i , such that $x = \{F, C_f, \mathbf{a}\}$, and as a output the indenter penetration in the sample, i.e. the penetration depth h . Parametrization and modelling is obtained by physics-informed data-driven approach, i.e. an hybrid method, where the functional form of the model is chosen based on contact mechanics, and model parameters are estimated by orthogonal distance regression (Maculotti et al 2024b), i.e.:

$$h(F) = h^* + \sqrt[m]{F/\alpha} \quad (3.1),$$

where $\vartheta = \{h^*, m, \alpha\}$ are the material dependent DT parameters, and h^* for the loading portion of the indentation curve is the first contact point, and for the unloading portion of the indentation curve is the residual indentation depth.

The scope of the DT is to provide a quality control of the measurement process, and to automatically identify out of controls.

This is obtained by realizing the DT for a CRM, i.e. SiO₂. Reference materials are typically calibrated by national metrological institutes for Young modulus by frequency methods. Accordingly, it is of interest not only to predict the penetration depth h , but also to predict the associated E_{IT} . This allows a statistical quality control on the calibrated value.

Such control requires the evaluation of measurement uncertainty of the DT. This is obtained by the application of the LPU approach.

First, relevant influence factors are identified, Figure 10 summarizes them, and then, they are statistically modelled, as reported in Table 1.

Figure 10. Influence Factors of nanoindentation (Maculotti et al 2024c).

Accordingly, the DT is established by the P2V twinning, which allows estimating the $\{h^*, m, \alpha\}$ for the different portions of the indentation curve. It is worth noticing that uncertainty of the estimated parameters, and the residual variance allows catering for epistemic uncertainty contributions. In particular, the ODR minimizes the orthogonal distance of errors on the regressor and the estimate, respectively, δ and ε , for the explicit model

$$h = f(F + \delta; \boldsymbol{\vartheta}) + \varepsilon \quad (3.2).$$

Table 1. Most relevant uncertainty variables and their assigned probability distribution: nanoindentation.

Uncertainty contributor	Probability distribution	Source
Force	Normal	reproducibility
Penetration depth	Normal	Accuracy
Frame Compliance	Normal	Calibration
Area shape function parameters	Normal	Calibration
Contact Stiffness	Normal	Fitting
Poisson Ratio (sample and indenter)	Uniform	Estimated
Young modulus of indenter	Uniform	Estimated
Texture	Normal	Reproducibility
Material parameters $\{h^*, m, \alpha\}$	Normal	Fitting

Next, uncertainty evaluation is performed following Section 2.1.1 by applying the LPU to the estimated penetration depth, i.e.:

$$u^2_h = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial h}{\partial F} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial \delta} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial \vartheta} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial \varepsilon} \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} u^2_F & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & ms\delta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Sigma_\vartheta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & u^2_h + mse \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial h}{\partial F} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial \delta} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial \vartheta} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial \varepsilon} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.3),$$

where u^2_F is the variance of F , combining the accuracy and the reproducibility, Σ_ϑ is the covariance matrix of estimated model parameters ϑ , $ms\delta$ and mse represent the mean square of the residuals δ and ε , and u^2_h is the accuracy of the penetration depth sensor.

The approach allows estimating the prediction uncertainty of simulated indentation curves on a reference material. Figure 11 shows the results on a calibrated SiO_2 sample, for an Anton Paar STeP6 platform hosted at Politecnico di Torino. The model is trained, i.e. the P2V twinning is established, on an experimental dataset consisting of 16 indentations on a NPL-calibrated SiO_2 sample.

Figure 11. Prediction Intervals for the average system response: DT of nanoindentation system. Confidence intervals at 95% confidence level.

The result can be leveraged to obtain further material characterization, e.g. in terms of estimated of Young modulus, i.e. the Indentation modulus E_{IT} :

$$E_{IT} = \frac{1 - \nu_s^2}{\left(\frac{2\sqrt{A_p(h_{c,max})}}{S\sqrt{\pi}} - \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i} \right)} \quad (3.4),$$

where ν_s is the sample Poisson's ratio, ν_i and E_i are the indenter Poisson's ratio and Young modulus, S is the sample contact stiffness, and $A_p(h_{c,max})$ is the projected contact area at the maximum penetration depth. Uncertainty of the mechanical response expected by the system through the DT can be evaluated by applying the LPU to Eq. (3.4) considering that the penetration depth uncertainty is estimated by Eq. (3.3), and that S is defined as $\frac{1}{S} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial h}|_{h=h_{max}} - C_f$.

Uncertainty contributions for the area shape function parameters and the frame compliance can be obtained by calibration (Maculotti et al 2024c), while for the contact stiffness also LPU shall be applied to the relevant model (Barbato et al 2017).

While computational details can be found in (Barbato et al 2017) for the application of LPU to evaluate the uncertainty of the indentation modulus, here it is worth to mention that the uncertainty of E_{IT} for indirect machine verification shall be smaller than 5% of the calibrated value (73.3 GPa).

Results show that the DT-related standard uncertainty of the expected sample response, i.e. the epistemic and traceability contribution, for the E_{IT} is 1.71 GPa, while the statistically estimated reproducibility (standard deviation of the 16 training data) is 0.13 GPa. The overall combined expanded uncertainty results as of $U(E_{IT}) = 2.72$ GPa, which corresponds to a relative uncertainty of 3.7%, smaller than the limit of 5% required by ISO 14577-2.

4 Case Study 2: 3D Robotic Measurements

The main objective of this case study is to assess the measurement uncertainty associated with a 3D robotic system used for dimensional inspection tasks. The system integrates an external sensor mounted on a robot arm, and is representative of flexible metrology solutions increasingly adopted in industrial environments. Figure 12 shows the measurement chain implemented in the DT and Figure 13 the creation workflow. Given the presence of multiple sources of uncertainty—stemming from both the robot and the sensor—accurate uncertainty evaluation is essential for ensuring reliable measurement results.

The uncertainty evaluation follows a Monte Carlo (MC) propagation approach. This methodology allows for the simulation of multiple possible system configurations based on identified uncertainty sources and their probability distributions. The main contributors considered are:

- The kinematic and dynamic behaviour of the robot,
- The intrinsic uncertainty of the sensor,
- The relative position and orientation of the sensor with respect to the robot flange.

Figure 12. Schematic representation of the Measurement chain.

Figure 13. 3D robotic measurement Digital Twin workflow.

A detailed characterisation of the main sources of uncertainty was performed:

- The sensor was evaluated using traceable artefacts to quantify its measurement uncertainty under different conditions.
- The robot was analysed to capture positioning repeatability and accuracy, with attention to variations caused by load and path-dependent dynamics.
- The sensor-to-robot transformation was calibrated and its variability quantified, since it strongly influences the final measurement accuracy.

To accurately model and propagate the sensor's contribution to the measurement uncertainty, a systematic characterisation process was carried out. The methodology was designed to generalise well to different sensors and setups, and to provide a traceable, repeatable means of capturing both systematic errors and precision across the sensor's full working range.

4.1 Sensor Characterisation Methodology

The procedure is based on the use of a series of calibrated gauge blocks, covering the full vertical measurement range of the sensor. In this case, blocks of 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70 mm in height were used. For each block, the following steps were carried out:

1. **Spatial Coverage:** Each gauge block was placed sequentially at three

horizontal positions within the sensor's field of view—left, centre, and right—thus covering spatial variability across the sensor plane (see Figure 15).

2. **Automated Acquisition:** At each position, 1000 measurements were automatically acquired. The process was fully automated and completed within approximately 5 minutes per block position.
3. **Height Computation and Averaging:** For each of the 1000 captures, the height of the gauge block was computed using the sensor's defined height extraction method. The mean height was then computed for each position. This step involved minimal computational resources and was typically completed in about 1 minute.
4. **Error Analysis:** The deviation between the nominal height of the gauge block and the measured mean value was calculated to assess **systematic error**, while the standard deviation of the measurements provided an estimate of **measurement precision**. To evaluate **local accuracy**, the deviation at each X position was compared against a linear fit across the three positions, allowing assessment of any spatial bias or tilt.

4.2 Robot Kinematic and Sensor Referencing Calibration

The calibration process for the robotic measurement system comprises two critical elements:

- Kinematic calibration of the robot, and
- Referencing (extrinsic calibration) between the robot and the sensor.

To achieve this, a calibrated artefact consisting of four high-precision spheres (also known as a “4-ball artefact”) is used. The geometry of this artefact is previously characterized by a coordinate measuring machine (CMM), providing metrological traceability to the calibration chain.

The artefact is placed within the robot's workspace and scanned using the mounted 3D sensor. Importantly, the scan is repeated across multiple robot configurations and scanning trajectories, ensuring that a wide range of poses and joint-space variations are captured. This diversity of poses allows for the robust identification of both:

- The intrinsic geometric parameters of the robot, including joint offsets, link lengths, and mechanical misalignments, and
- The extrinsic transformation between the robot's tool center point (TCP) and the sensor's coordinate system.

By minimizing the residuals between the measured and nominal sphere positions (from the CMM data), a global optimization is performed to estimate the kinematic parameters and their associated uncertainties. This is the foundation for constructing the uncertainty distributions used later in the Monte Carlo-based measurement process.

This calibration procedure is essential to:

- Ensure that the digital twin accurately represents the physical system.
- Provide traceable uncertainty quantification throughout the measurement process.
- Enable reliable referencing between the robot and the sensor, crucial for

consistent point cloud generation.

This process is illustrated in Figure 14, where the 4-ball artefact is shown in the robot's workspace, and different scanning trajectories are depicted.

Figure 14. Process to calibrate robot.

4.3 Generation of an Error Map

This procedure yielded a detailed characterisation of the sensor response across its working volume, accounting for both vertical range and lateral position. A grid of systematic errors and standard deviations was constructed from the nominal-measured deviations across the different block heights and lateral positions.

To enable real-time uncertainty propagation within the Monte Carlo simulations, a lightweight **interpolation and extrapolation model** was built. For any arbitrary measurement point in the sensor's field (in XZ coordinates), the systematic error and its associated standard deviation could be estimated using a **piecewise linear interpolation**. This approach ensures a rapid and reasonably accurate estimation of the sensor's local behaviour, without requiring costly recalibration or re-computation (see Figure 15).

To reduce the computational cost of repeated evaluations during the MC simulations, a surrogate model of the sensor was developed. This model replicates the sensor's behaviour based on a limited set of high-fidelity simulations or experimental results. Once validated, it enables rapid estimation of the sensor's response under varying conditions, significantly improving the efficiency of the uncertainty propagation process.

The final uncertainty estimates obtained through the MC propagation were validated experimentally. This was done using traceable artefacts placed in the robot's working volume. Comparison between the predicted uncertainty and the measured deviations provided confidence in the robustness of the model and the effectiveness of the proposed methodology (see Figure 16)

Figure 15. Process to characterize the error sources of 2d sensor triangulator

Figure 16. Example of use of the digital twin.

4.4 Uncertainty Evaluation

In this case study, measurement uncertainty is assessed using a Monte Carlo simulation method, in accordance with JCGM 101:2008 – Evaluation of measurement data – Supplement 1 to the “Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement” – Propagation of distributions using a Monte Carlo method. This approach is integrated directly into the robotic measurement workflow through a fully characterized digital twin of the system (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Monte Carlo Simulation for Uncertainty evaluation in robotic measurements.

The digital twin encompasses all relevant components of the robotic measurement setup: robot kinematics, scanner characteristics, and calibration artifacts. Each of these components is associated with uncertainty values derived from the calibration process, represented in the Calibration block of Figure 16.

The Monte Carlo simulation cycle is executed in parallel with each measurement. That is, for every actual measurement taken by the robotic system (see the Measurement block in Figure 16), the digital twin generates thousands of simulated instances by randomly sampling from the input distributions (uncertainty models) of the system parameters. This allows the system to propagate uncertainty through the full measurement chain in real time.

The result of this process is a 3D point cloud representing the scanned object, where each measured point is assigned a quantified uncertainty. This enhances traceability and transparency, and enables downstream applications (e.g. tolerance verification, process control) to factor in measurement uncertainty explicitly.

The main advantages of this methodology are:

- Context-specific uncertainty estimation: each measurement carries its own uncertainty, dependent on the system state at the moment of acquisition.
- Compliance with international standards (JCGM 101:2008).
- Automation-ready: the uncertainty estimation is embedded in the digital twin and measurement pipeline, enabling use in industrial settings without additional manual analysis.

5 Case Study 3: Rotary Table for Angular Measurements

The rotary table (see Figure 4) is based on a main measuring system, that is a dual-encoder (Figure 18) Acquisition System where angular position is acquired

using two high-precision incremental optical encoders mounted in a differential configuration. This setup allows for the reciprocal cancellation of systematic interpolation and graduation errors, significantly reducing the angular measurement uncertainty.

Figure 18. Rotary table for angular measurement main measuring system: dual encoder.

The reference table is designed to work in conjunction with high-precision autocollimators (e.g., ELCOMAT HR) for absolute angular referencing and alignment procedures.

The schema shown in Figure 19 shows the different error sources that affects the measurand's accuracy which is the angle position.

Figure 19 5 Ms of error sources affecting angle measurements.

5.1 Geometrical Error Sources

Despite the high structural precision of the reference rotary table, residual geometrical errors—such as parasitic motions and misalignments—can significantly impact angular measurements, especially at sub-arcsecond resolution. The Small Displacement Torsor (SDT) formalism was adopted to the reference rotary table. This framework represents the deviation of the table's terminal element from its ideal position using six components: three small

translations (T_x, T_y, T_z) and three small rotations (R_x, R_y, R_z). These are all functions of the rotation angle and capture effects such as radial and axial runouts, tilt (wobble), and angular positioning errors. By measuring these components through 8 capacitive sensors mounted on the upper and the lower track of the table (Figure 20) and the dual encoder (R_z), we can reconstruct the motion of the rotating surface and quantify the impact of geometric defects on angular measurements. This modeling enables both correction of raw measurements and dynamic uncertainty evaluation.

Figure 20. Capacitive sensors mounted on the reference

5.2 Small Displacement Torsor Calculation

The process involves acquiring data from eight capacitive sensors $\vec{M} = [\delta_1, \delta_i, \delta_8]^T$, where δ_i deviations from the metrological reference along the direction perpendicular to the surface. This information is projected onto an analysis basis defined as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_{xn} \\ N_{yn} \\ N_{zn} \\ -Z_n N_{yn} + Y_n N_{zn} \\ -X_n N_{zn} + Z_n N_{xn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.1),$$

that accounts for the orientation of each sensor, allowing for the decoupling of displacements along each axis. The resulting errors are obtained in five degrees of freedom, as the error along the Z-axis (axial direction) corresponds to the angular accuracy—trueness—already provided by the dual encoder system. The results are expressed in micrometres for the translations (T) and microradians for the rotation components.

5.3 Results

Table 2 presents the measurements from the eight capacitive sensors. The measured deviation vector is then projected using the Gram-Schmidt, resulting in the computed small displacement torsor (SDT) shown in Table 3. The SDT quantifies the parasitic motions that affect the rotation of the reference table.

Table 2. Measurements

<i>cap1</i>	<i>cap2</i>	<i>cap3</i>	<i>cap4</i>	<i>cap5</i>	<i>cap6</i>	<i>cap7</i>	<i>cap8</i>
29.79	-24.60	23.77	-18.01	16.926	-19.83	23.17	-25.17
29.82	-24.59	23.76	-17.96	16.94	-19.82	23.18	-25.18
29.54	-24.37	24.42	18.05	16.32	20.08	21.71	-25.04

Table 3. Computed SDT.

$T_x / \mu\text{m}$	$T_y / \mu\text{m}$	$T_z / \mu\text{m}$	$R_x / \mu\text{rad}$	$R_y / \mu\text{rad}$
7.059	4.811	-0.127	-47.600	20.378
7.091	4.842	-0.129	-47.712	20.495
7.141	4.485	-0.434	-47.360	16.236

5.4 Virtual Experiment of the Reference Rotary Table Digital Twin

As an initial step toward the implementation of the digital twin, virtual experiment was modelled, which constitutes a fundamental component of the digital twin framework for the reference structure (Figure 21). The first objective is to simulate the angular position by generating two rotational signals and applying the working principle of the dual encoder system. This simulation incorporates the main error sources affecting the dual encoder, particularly those influencing its measurand—angular position.

Figure 21. Structure of angular plate DT framework.

Interpolation errors are defined as

$$\varepsilon(\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^N A_n \sin(np\theta + \Phi_n) \quad (5.2),$$

where θ is the encoder angle in radians or degrees, p is the number of periods per revolution (linked to number of interpolated lines), A_n is the amplitude and Φ_n is the phase shift of n -th harmonic (in arcsec).

The simulated mobile angle is expressed as $\theta_{mobile} + \varepsilon(\theta)$ and the simulated fixed angle is $\theta_{fixe} + \varepsilon(\theta)$. The angular position α is obtained by integrating the difference between θ_{mobile} and the θ_{fixe} over a full revolution, i.e:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{360} \left\{ \int_0^{360} (\theta_{mobile} - \theta_{fixe}) d\theta \right\} \quad (5.3).$$

This working principle aims to eliminate systematic errors. A complete revolution corresponds to 12,500 measurements. In the real system, the entire acquisition and processing operation takes approximately 5 to 8 seconds (with each measurement occurring every 90 ms), whereas the simulation achieves the same in 4 seconds. These simulated angle signals are further corrected by accounting for geometric errors modelled previously and thermal effects (including drift and gradients). The corrected data then serves as input to an estimator filter. A first attempt at estimation was conducted using a Kalman filter.

In the context of the reference rotary table digital twin, the variables are mapped to the general Digital Twin formalism introduced in Eq. (1.1) and Eq. (1.3) as follows:

- **Measurement:**
 - Raw encoder angle signals, corrected encoder angle (after geometric and thermal compensation), Kalman-filtered angle estimate
- **Measurand:**
 - True angular position of the rotary table
- **System parameters:**
 - parasitic displacement errors (T_x, T_y, R_x, R_y) from the Small Displacement Torsor (SDT) model, temperature gradient-induced drift, encoder interpolation error
- **Model parameters:**
 - Kalman filter parameters (Q, R), harmonic parameters of interpolation error model (amplitude A_n , phase Φ_n), thermal drift coefficients

5.5 Kalman Filter Application for Position Angle Estimation

To enhance the accuracy of angular position estimation in the virtual experiment, a Kalman filter was implemented as a first state estimation approach. The filter operates on corrected angle data, where the simulated dual encoder measurements are first compensated for geometric and thermal errors:

$$\alpha_{corrected} = \theta_{simulated}(k) + \delta\theta_T(k) + \delta\theta_{geo}(k) \quad (5.2)$$

$$X_k = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_k \\ \omega_k \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.3)$$

$$\alpha(t') = \alpha(t) + \int_t^{t'} \omega(\tau) d\tau \quad (5.4)$$

The virtual experiment is applied on a 24-faced polygon (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Angular plate test artifact: Polygon with 24 faces.

The obtained results are represented in Table 4. The filter produces an estimated angular position over time with improved smoothness and stability compared to raw measurements. It enables better convergence over the 24-face polygon, where each face measurement serves as an anchor for evaluating performance.

Table 4. Kalman filter results

Sample	Angle Corrected (°)	Angle Kalman (°)	Error (°)
1	152.763869	152.755414	-0.008456
2	137.943722	137.943722	0.000000
3	123.268138	123.268138	-0.000000
4	108.935732	108.935723	-0.000009
5	94.133931	94.133942	0.000011
6	78.988179	78.988190	0.000011
7	63.457734	63.457745	0.000012
8	47.429319	47.429334	0.000015
9	31.507456	31.507455	-0.000001
10	16.320070	16.320051	-0.000020

5.6 Uncertainty assessment of the reference rotary table digital twin

A GUM-compliant Monte Carlo method was implemented to evaluate the uncertainty of the angular position estimated by the reference rotary table's digital twin. The simulated angle corresponds to the fused measurement result obtained by applying an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) to corrected observations that integrate data from the double encoder, capacitive probes (used to extract small displacement torsors), and a thermal probe monitoring temperature gradients.

The uncertainty contributors were modelled using Type A (experimental) or Type B (model-based or manufacturer-provided) distributions:

- Geometric errors from parasitic displacements (T_x , T_y , R_x , R_y), derived from SDT analysis of capacitive sensor measurements, were modelled using normal distributions, with standard deviations obtained from high-resolution repeatability tests.
- Thermal drift was modelled using a linear thermal expansion profile, based on simulated gradients across the table surface.

- Encoder interpolation and quantization errors were implicitly accounted for in the corrected observations input to the EKF.
- Kalman filter estimation noise was naturally included via its recursive structure and process noise covariance.

A total of 10,000 Monte Carlo simulations were performed. In each iteration, all uncertainty contributors were randomly generated and propagated through the geometric and thermal correction models. The corrected angles were then filtered using an EKF, and the final angular position (at a fixed index $t = 49$) was recorded.

The histogram of estimated angles (Figure 23) shows a centred and symmetric Gaussian distribution, with a standard deviation of 0.010 arcseconds, demonstrating excellent consistency and low bias. The corresponding 95% coverage interval is ± 0.020 arcseconds ($k = 2$).

These results confirm that the combined modelling and fusion strategy offers high-confidence angular positioning, even in the presence of multiple physical uncertainties, under static measurement conditions.

Figure 23. Histogram of Monte Carlo simulation for the estimated angle with the Digital Twin of the rotary table for primary angle measurements.

6 Case Study 4: Electrical Measurements

6.1 Sheath currents in high voltage cable systems

For this DT the Monte Carlo method has been applied for the uncertainty evaluation.

For the application of the Monte Carlo method, the interest variables y_i have been defined as a function of certain input parameters x_i . For the case of the DT under study, the input parameters considered are the uncertainty contributors listed later in Table 5, along with their assigned probability distribution.

The model used for the Monte Carlo method is run repeatedly with the input

variables following the specified distributions. With this process, results for the y_i interest variables are obtained. These results follow a distribution from which the uncertainty can be determined.

The Monte Carlo method is useful when the analytical models used are constituted by complex expressions, therefore complicating the uncertainty propagation calculations. With this method, it is not necessary to perform the complex uncertainty propagation calculations for this DT. In Figure 24, a schematic representation of the Monte Carlo method is shown.

Figure 24. Schematic representation of the Monte Carlo method.

The uncertainty evaluation method is executed in the following way.

Firstly, the Monte Carlo model implemented, which is programmed inside the proper software of the DT, is run in the following two steps:

1. The model is run considering the uncertainty sources individually, to evaluate their effect on the uncertainty trend of the results. Furthermore, the impact of each uncertainty source on the output is compared, to determine which are the most relevant sources.
2. The model is run considering all the uncertainty sources at the same time, to analyze their effects in the results. This allows the uncertainty propagation within the DT. Therefore, the global uncertainty of the DT is estimated.

The uncertainty sources to be considered individually or altogether can be selected on a user interface of the DT. Once the Monte Carlo method is executed the results are available in a raw file.

Secondly, the data obtained in the raw file generated by the DT, are processed in a developed Matlab script. With this script, the average value and the standard deviation for each of the output variables are calculated.

Thirdly, the results generated with the Matlab result are stored in an Excel file. All the information gathered in this file is used for the representation of the results in graphics and for the data analysis.

In the following, a study on the uncertainty of the results obtained with DT is presented, applying the uncertainty evaluation method considering the previous three steps.

For the uncertainty evaluation of the interest variables previously identified and characterized, a sensitivity analysis of them is performed, analyzing the influence that they have on the results obtained.

The aim of this study is to determine the weight of each of the variables considered on the uncertainty of the results. In this way, the variables with less weight can be given less importance and, if necessary, they can be disregarded in the computation processes of the evaluation of the uncertainty and in the obtention of results with the DT.

For the DT under study in this project, the computational processes are not very demanding. Therefore, the aim of this study for this specific case is to identify which variables must be considered with greater or lesser care in the parametrization processes of the DT. As the computational requirements are not unaffordable, the simplification of any variable is not considered, neither on the uncertainty evaluation process nor in the calculation processes of the DT.

In this DT, major weight in the uncertainty values of the output variables is associated with the uncertainty inherent to the input variables that have been taken into account in this study.

The uncertainty resulting from the calculation methods used in the DT is assumed to be less than 1%. This uncertainty is primarily due to the numerical methods used for matrix inversion and integral calculations, for the electrical parameters estimation of the power cables.

The software has been validated for some cases of power lines configurations, taking as reference the results obtained from analytic formulas, by applying matrix methods based on symmetrical components. Furthermore, the validation of the electrical parameters has been done by comparing different power cable configurations with results obtained by finite element methods.

In this study, among all the uncertainty contributors identified for the DT, the most relevant ones have been considered. These variables are listed on Table 5 along with their assigned probability distribution.

Table 5. Most relevant uncertainty variables and their assigned probability distribution.

Uncertainty contributor	Probability distribution
Thermal resistivity of the soil	Uniform
Relative permittivity of the main insulation	Uniform
Electrical resistivity of the conductors	Uniform
Ambient temperature	Uniform
Cable laying (cable to cable distance)	Uniform
Cable dimensions (dimensions of each of the layers)	Uniform

Besides the variables listed in Table 5, other variables were identified but they have not been included in this analysis due to the following reasons:

- Heat transmission coefficients: the values used in the calculations are given by applicable regulations.

- Resistance in the earth connections: these resistance values only affect the results in fault conditions. The effect that they have on the steady state is negligible, therefore, they have not been considered in this study.
- Outer layer of the cable temperature: it is calculated internally by the DT based on other inputs.
- Temperature in each layer of the cable: it is calculated internally by the DT based on other inputs.
- Current by the sheaths: it is an output of the DT.
- Current by the output conductor: it is only considered in dynamic calculations. For static calculations, the load value of the cable in percentage terms has been specified. The current through the active conductor is then calculated, therefore, it is treated as a result.
- Cable lengths and on-site joint and terminals emplacements: variable considered to be of very little importance in its contribution to the estimation of uncertainty.
- Voltage: variable considered to be of very little importance in its contribution to the estimation of uncertainty.

For the case of the study that has been carried out, an underground high voltage power line has been considered and simulated on the DT. In Figure 25 the layout of the power line is shown.

Figure 25. Layout of the power line simulated on the DT for the evaluation of the uncertainty of the results.

In the study of the uncertainty associated to the results, the influence of the variables indicated in Table 5 has been characterized for the actual state of development of the DT and for the simulated power line. The output parameters (results) considered are the following.

- Currents by the active conductors of the three phases.
- Currents by the sheaths for section 1 (with cross-bonding configuration, between substation A and joint CE3).
- Currents by the sheaths for section 2 (with single-point configuration, between joint CE3 and substation B).

The three phases of the power system are labelled as J0, J4 and J8 in the following graphics.

6.1.1 Results obtained in the evaluation of uncertainty sources individually to study their effect on the outputs uncertainty trends

To detect the trend (sensitivity) of the behaviour of the results with the aim of determining which variables have a greater impact on the results, the procedure

is as follows.

On a first step, a single input variable is selected, and its assigned probability distribution is considered. Afterwards, and for the different values of uncertainty adopted by the variable, the model is run a high number of times. For this specific case of study, it is run 10.000 times. Once the model has been executed, the distribution obtained as an output is observed. Increasing progressively the uncertainty of the input variable, it can be studied the variation of the uncertainty of the output, if there is any.

The Monte Carlo method is executed for different uncertainty levels, which are assigned to each of the six input parameters that were shown in Table 5.

The results obtained for each of the variables are shown below.

➤ **Results for the input variable soil thermal resistivity**

In Figure 26, the trend of the standard deviation for the three output parameters considered is shown. The distribution is centred on a soil thermal resistivity of 1 K m/W.

For this variable and for the rest, the standard deviation values are shown on the y-axis, while the variation of the input variable is shown in the x-axis. As it can be seen, for the sheath currents, when the variation of the input variable (thermal soil resistivity) is increased, the uncertainty increases. On the other hand, for the active conductor current, the increment of the variation of the inputs does not produce a significant rise on the uncertainties.

Figure 26. Standard deviation trend obtained for the three output parameters considered for the three phases. a) Active conductor currents. b) Sheath currents for section 1. c) Sheath currents for section 2.

➤ **Results for the input variable soil thermal resistivity**

In Figure 27 the results for the analysis when the input variable is the ambient temperature are shown. The distribution is centred on 22°C.

It can be observed that the impact that a rise on the uncertainty of the temperature has a limited impact on the active conductor current. On the other hand, it can be seen that it produces an increment on the sheath currents uncertainty.

Figure 27. Standard deviation trend obtained for the three output parameters considered for the three phases. a) Active conductor currents. b) Sheath currents for section 1. c) Sheath currents for section 2.

➤ **Results for the input variable cable laying (cable-to-cable distance)**

In Figure 28, the results for the analysis using the cable-to-cable distance as input variable are shown. In this case, the variations are applied in percentage terms to the position of each cable, which defines the cable-to-cable distance. The distribution is centred on a 0% variation, this is, the theoretical laying of the cables.

It can be observed that the effect that this variable has on the output variables is quite significant. This is caused by the influence that the distance between cables has on the magnetic coupling between all the conductors involved.

Figure 28. Standard deviation trend obtained for the three output parameters considered for the three phases. a) Active conductor currents. b) Sheath currents for section 1. c) Sheath currents for section 2.

➤ **Results for the input variable cable diameter**

The results obtained when the input variable is the cable diameter are shown in Figure 29. In this case, the variation is applied to each layer in terms of percentage. The distribution is centred on a 0% variation of the dimensions of the cable, in other words, the specified dimensions of the cable.

It can be seen that the diameter has a clear effect on the uncertainty of the output and it affects all the outputs in a similar way.

Figure 29. Standard deviation trend obtained for the three output parameters considered for the three phases. a) Active conductor currents. b) Sheath currents for section 1. c) Sheath currents for section 2.

➤ **Results for the input variable electrical resistivity**

In Figure 30, the results for the analysis with the electrical resistivity as input are shown. The distribution is centred on 0 p.u., which represents the specified electrical resistivity for each conductor.

It can be observed that the impact of this variable on the sheath currents of the cross-bonding section is limited. On the other hand, it does have impact on the current through the active conductor and the sheath currents of the single-point section.

Figure 30. Standard deviation trend obtained for the three output parameters considered for the three phases. a) Active conductor currents. b) Sheath currents for section 1. c) Sheath currents for section 2.

➤ **Results for the input variable relative permittivity**

In Figure 31, the results for the input variable relative permittivity are shown. The distribution is centred on 0 p.u., which represents no variation at all taking as reference the specified value.

As the variations of this input variable affect the leakage currents, it has a clear impact on the currents of the sheath for both the single and the cross-bonding configurations. It also influences the current through the active conductors, since the leakage currents originate from them.

Figure 31. Standard deviation trend obtained for the three output parameters considered for the three phases. a) Active conductor currents. b) Sheath currents for section 1. c) Sheath currents for section 2.

➤ **Results obtained in the evaluation of uncertainty sources individually for the identification of the most relevant ones.**

For the identification of the most relevant uncertainty sources, the most characteristic values for the input's uncertainties were considered. In this way, reference values for the input variables are used as a starting point for comparing the standard deviation values obtained for the uncertainty of the output variables. For each of the reference values, the standard deviation of the uncertainty has been obtained from the graphics presented on the previous section.

In Table 6 the maximum standard deviation values obtained for the three output variables considered are shown, taking as reference the most characteristic uncertainty value of each of the input variables.

As can be observed, the variables with greater impact on the final result of the output parameter **current through the active conductor** are the cable diameter and the relative permittivity. Meanwhile, the inputs with the least impact on the output are the thermal conductivity of the soil, the ambient temperature, the cable laying and the electrical resistivity.

The variables with greater impact on the final result of the output parameter **sheath current for the cross-bonding section** are the cable diameter, the relative permittivity of the main insulation, and the cable laying. On the other hand, the variables with less influence on said output are the thermal conductivity of the soil, the ambient temperature and the electrical resistivity.

The variables with greater impact on the final result of the output parameter **sheath current for the single-point section** are the cable diameter and the relative permittivity of the main insulation. Meanwhile, the least contributing inputs are the thermal resistivity of the soil, the ambient temperature, the cable laying and the electrical resistivity.

Table 6. Outputs uncertainty (three phase maximum) for each of the input variables considered individually.

Input variable	Reference value for the variation of the input variable	Output's uncertainties		
		Active conductor current standard deviation	Sheath current standard deviation for cross-bonding section	Sheath current standard deviation for single-point section
Thermal resistivity of the soil	$\pm 0.4 \text{ K m/W}$	0.0049%	0.17%	0.0006%
Ambient temperature	$\pm 6 \text{ K}$	0.0050%	0.39%	0.0016%
Cable to cable distance	$\pm 5 \%$	0.0096%	2.21%	0.0053%
Cable diameter variation (of each layer)	$\pm 5 \%$	0.072%	5.23%	8.64%
Electrical resistivity	$\pm 5\%$	0.0050%	0.11%	0.0003%
Relative permittivity	± 0.1	0.048%	3.45%	5.76%

➤ **Results obtained in the evaluation of the uncertainty propagation within the DT.**

For the uncertainty propagation within the DT considering all the uncertainty sources at the same time, the most characteristic uncertainty values for the six input variables were also considered. For comparison purposes, in Table 7 the individual results obtained in Table 6 are shown together with the uncertainty propagation values obtained here.

For the three output variables, when the effect of all the input variables is considered all at once, the standard deviation value obtained is superior to the ones obtained when the variables were considered one at a time.

To determine the final uncertainty value, the standard deviation (σ in percentage terms) for the three output variables is multiplied by a factor of 2. In this way, the uncertainty values are the following: for the **active current** $\pm 1.74\%$, **sheath current for cross-bonding section** $\pm 13.24\%$ and **sheath current for single-point section** $\pm 20.84\%$.

For the estimation of the uncertainty indicated, a case study of a typical line has

been used as a starting point. For the validation of the DT, the uncertainty estimation process adopted for this line will be repeated, considering at least two real lines. For the new uncertainty estimations, it will be useful to use the synthetic datasets, in order to test the uncertainty estimation method considered for the DT validation process.

Based on the estimated uncertainty of the input variables under study, the results provide an estimation of the influence of the dynamic effect on temperature calculations involved in the DT, when the dynamic model is used and the results are considered at a fixed point in time, without significant variations in load level during the preceding time intervals.

Table 7. Outputs uncertainty (three phase maximum) for each of the input variables considered individually, and for the six input variables considered altogether.

Input variable	Reference value for the variation of the input variable	Output's uncertainties					
		Active conductor current standard deviation		Sheath current standard deviation for cross-bonding section		Sheath current standard deviation for single-point section	
		For individual inputs	All inputs	For individual inputs	All inputs	For individual inputs	All inputs
Thermal resistivity of the soil	± 0.4 K m/W	0.0049%	0.87%	0.17%	6.62%	0.0006%	10.42%
Ambient temperature	± 6 K	0.0050%		0.39%		0.0016%	
Cable to cable distance	$\pm 5\%$	0.0096%		2.21%		0.0053%	
Cable diameter variation (of each layer)	$\pm 5\%$	0.072%		5.23%		8.64%	
Electrical resistivity	$\pm 5\%$	0.0050%		0.11%		0.0003%	
Relative permittivity	± 0.1	0.048%		3.45%		5.76%	

6.2 Internal Arc Test

6.2.1 Models implemented

The short circuit withstand test was simulated using two methods. **The Finite Difference Method (FDM) provides only the average value of the output pressure and temperature but can be resolved within a short time and with minimal computational resources. Instead, the Finite Volumen Method (FVM) gives a detailed spatial description of the phenomenon, including the pressure, temperature, and air velocity, with the cost of requiring more computational time and resources. Although each method provides different outcomes, both**

methods are based on the same fundamental equations.

Figure 32. Schematic of the physical model. It shows the arc heat Q_1 , the mass m_i and volume V_i , the velocity components u_i , v_i and w_i , and the pressure p_i and temperature T_i , what $i=\{1,2,3\}$ for each compartment. m_{12} and m_{23} are the mass fluxes between compartments.

Figure 32 shows a schematic of the physical model considering a switchgear with two compartments, one at high pressure (the “Arc Compartment”, where the arc is produced), and the other where the gas can flow (the “Exhaust Compartment”). The exhausted gas is ventilated to the “Installation Room”, a volume greatly bigger than the others two. **The model can be represented from the equations of ideal gas, mass, momentum and energy conservation equations.** From the analysis of the model implemented, several uncertainties sources were identified, such as dimensional measurements, specific heat capacity, initial gas density, pressure and temperature, arc voltage and current, discharge coefficient, thermal transfer coefficient and laminar viscosity. Not all sources may be relevant in the uncertainty budget; **a sensitivity analysis of the model was implemented which is explained next.**

6.2.2 Monte Carlo Method for uncertainty estimation of overpressure

Because the virtual entity can be simulated with a parametric model, the IAT DT will use the Monte Carlo Method (MCM, described in Guide for Uncertainty in Measurements: Supplement 1) to obtain the mean and standard deviation of the overpressure.

To accomplish this a dataset for each input parameter is generated using random samples with an appropriate known distribution type. From the output parameter’s distribution, the value of the measurand is determined.

The different uncertainty sources described in the previous section, Table 8 and Table 9 list these sources. Note that not all sources will be measured in the physical environment and for those cases their distributions and typical values would be taken from literature. Table 9 shows the range informed in the

literature for those parameters.

Table 8. Uncertainties sources from the equations for the finite difference calculation. Normal distribution is considered with $k=2$.

Source	Symbol	Description	Probability distribution	Limit of distribution	Observation
Dimensional measurements	-	Resolution of the instruments and parallax error.	Rectangular	0.5 mm	Instrument resolution
Specific heat capacities	$c_v - c_p$	Deviations from a pure gas mixture.	Normal	1%	Literature
Initial gas density	ρ	Deviations from a pure gas mixture.	Normal	0.1%	Literature
Gas pressure	p	Initial pressures for ambient and compartment	Normal	5 hPa	Instrument accuracy
Voltage measurement	U	From the measurement instruments.	Normal	To be defined	Instrument accuracy
Current measurement	I	From the measurement instruments.	Normal	To be defined	Instrument accuracy
Gas temperature	T	Initial temperatures for ambient and compartment	Normal	1 K	Instrument accuracy

Table 9. Range of sources with rectangular probability distribution informed in the literature.

Source	Symbol	Description	Probability distribution	Range	Observation
Discharge coefficient	α_{out}	Coeff. that considers the shape of the opening.	Rectangular	0.6-0.75 (dimensionless)	Literature
Thermal transfer coefficient	k_p	Coeff. of electric energy to heat energy.	Rectangular	0.4-0.7 (dimensionless)	Literature
Laminar viscosity	μ	Deviations from a pure gas mixture.	Rectangular	$(1.8-2.0) \cdot 10^{-5}$ Pa s	Literature

6.2.3 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was made with the implementation of the MCM to the FDM. As mentioned GUM-Supplement 1, the distributions must have a size of at least $10^4/(1-p)$ elements, where p is the confidence interval chosen for the calculus. For a 0.68 confidence interval ($k=1$), $3.1 \cdot 10^4$ elements are needed. The distributions for the input parameters mentioned in the previous section are shown in Figure 33. Each of them has the above number of elements, and the mean and range values described in the previous section. For the standard deviation $\sigma = \sigma_{k=2}/2$, where $\sigma_{k=2}$ is the standard deviation presented in Table 8.

Figure 33. Distributions for $3.1 \cdot 10^4$ values for the input parameters.

With these distributions, $3.1 \cdot 10^4$ simulations were made, each with different input values. Figure 34 shows the result for the mean pressure inside the arc compartment with a maximum pressure of (0.605 ± 0.013) MPa. Because a simulation for each uncertainty source will be made for this sensitivity analysis, an alternative MCM with 10^3 elements for each distribution was made to reduce the computational time and evaluate the effect of reducing the number of elements. Figure 35 shows the results of this simulation. As can be seen, no significant difference with Figure 34 is present at the maximum value (0.606 ± 0.013) MPa.

Figure 34. Mean pressure for $3.1 \cdot 10^4$ iterations. A maximum value of (0.605 ± 0.013) MPa was reached.

Figure 35. Mean pressure for 10^3 iterations. A maximum value of (0.606 ± 0.013) MPa was reached.

On the one hand, comparing both values shows a relative error of $RE = 0.2\%$, taking the simulation with the greater number of iterations as the reference value. On the other hand, the simulation with 10^3 iterations has a coefficient of variation of $CV = \sigma_p/p = 2\%$, the same as the $3.1 \cdot 10^4$ iterations simulation. With these results we can conclude that for this case, a simulation with fewer iterations can be made without losing accuracy or precision.

6.2.4 Simplified uncertainty model

The result for the uncertainty calculation with a MCM with 10^3 iterations for the pressure inside the arc compartment with **all probability distributions for the sources included (now called Δp)** was compared with the result of the uncertainty calculated with just one of the probability distributions and the rest of the sources as a constant value equal to the mean value of the original distribution. Each of the last ones was called Δp_j , where j corresponds to the name of each distribution. These results are presented in Figure 36 as the ratio of $\Delta p_j / \Delta p$, the values inside the exclusion zone in red can be neglected, and they will be excluded as an uncertainty source for the model. **The 0.3 value corresponds to one third of the total uncertainty Δp , which for uncertainty values less or equal than that, the influence is negligible.**

In conclusion, the arc voltage (uR) and current (iR), the thermal transfer coefficient (k_p) and the discharge coefficient (α) can be used as an uncertainty source.

Figure 36. Results for the sensitivity analysis with 10^3 iterations for each simulation.

6.3 Quantum Voltage Standard

6.3.1 Proposed methodology

To implement the V2P connection and establish a closed feedback loop for updating the DT, measurements should be integrated with the data-driven model to dynamically adjust the model based on the system's actual behaviour. This requires the acquisition of data in real-time or a batch, a mechanism to update the digital twin based on new measurements, and an optimization process to iteratively adjust the controllable parameters.

The physical system has the following controllable parameters: amplitude, signal frequency, number of steps, sampling rate, and number of points per period. The initial configuration is used to generate the desired objective signal, and it is sampled in a batch with the digitizer. The measurements are used to create datasets and train the data-driven model that predicts the system behaviour based on the input parameters.

The error is calculated as the difference between the predicted and the theoretical signal. The uncertainty of the inputs is estimated with the Monte Carlo GUM-compliant method (MCM). For model uncertainty, the Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) method is used. Then, an optimization algorithm adjusts some of the controllable parameters to reduce the difference between the predicted and theoretical signals. Updated parameters are set in the physical system to regenerate the signal. The system continuously refines parameters to achieve

the desired performance. Figure 37 shows the workflow of the method used.

Figure 37. Virtual-to-Physical twinning application.

6.3.2 Selection of input parameters and evaluation of metrological characteristics

The input parameters define the uncertainty in the P2V connection. The Microwave frequency depends on the stability of Cesium and Rubidium atomic clocks, and is measured with a frequency counter. The signal frequency and sampling frequency are affected by jitter, since they rely on the stability of a digital PLL and are related to the atomic clocks.

The microwave power is estimated and verified with subsequent measurements using the calibration curve of the microwave synthesizer and the step width of the voltage-current characteristic curve. The value of the margin current can also be calculated using the step width.

The helium level is measured with a liquid helium level sensor, before and after running the experiment. This only applies in a wet system.

The gain and offset of the digitizers with their standard deviations are determined by previous characterizations.

The uncertainty of voltage measurements is related to the measuring instrument. We use high-accuracy instruments (Agilent 3458A, NI PXI5922, and a custom-made $\Sigma\Delta$ digitizer) to measure the QVS output and compare it with the DT output.

As the inputs have low correlation and their distributions are known, their uncertainty contribution is evaluated following the GUM, applying MCM.

The traceability for measurements is defined by the ISO/IEC 17025 standard. As the QVS digital twin represents the realization of a unit of the SI, the volt (V), the traceability is guaranteed in the definition of the SI. As stated before, the voltage of this primary standard depends only on fundamental constants such as h (the Planck constant) and e (the elementary charge), and on a known microwave frequency. The latter is traceable to the unit second (s) of the SI by an atomic clock.

We evaluate the accuracy, repeatability, and sensitivity according to the measurement system by direct comparison with the SI unit. Fidelity is represented by the voltage accuracy of measurements of the theoretical Josephson voltage.

For sensitivity evaluation, the inputs are modified in small percentages according to the parameter, considering that the output variation must be greater than the digitizer's uncertainty. To evaluate the metrological characteristics of the parameters, INTI proposes to follow the definitions from the GUM and VIM.

To ensure the quality of our method, we can compare the measurement results with the predictions of the data-based model. Both results must agree within their confidence intervals. The laboratory follows the ISO 17025:2017 to provide traceability and software validation, as stated in section 6.5.1 and section 7.11.2 of the ISO 17025:2017, the laboratory provides traceability and software validation.

6.3.3 Models

Different models were trained using TensorFlow and Keras to predict the quantum voltage steps of the signals.

➤ Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

An example is shown in Figure 38. The shape of the input layer is determined by the number of features in the dataset. The number of layers and neurons per layer set the complexity of the model. After each hidden layer, a dropout layer with a dropout rate equal to 0.2 is added to prevent overfitting. The output layer has only one neuron with a linear activation function because the result should be the prediction of one voltage (regression problem). Due to this, mean squared error (MSE) is chosen as the loss function and root mean squared error (RMSE) as the metric.

Figure 38. Example of neural network model used to make predictions of PJVS signals.

The other parameters used in this example are:

- **Activation function:** Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU).
- **Optimizer:** Adam, learning rate = 0.001.
- **Loss:** mean squared error (MSE).
- **Metric:** root mean squared error (RMSE).

- **Batch Size:** 16.
- **Epochs:** 300.

An important factor to consider is that these hyperparameters should be optimized to obtain the best results. Updates of the model will include variations to improve the performance.

➤ **Mixture Density Neural Network (MDNN)**

A Mixture Density Network is a neural network designed to model probability distributions over its outputs. Instead of predicting a single value (as in ordinary regression), an MDN predicts the parameters of a mixture model—usually a Gaussian mixture—so that for each input it outputs a full probability density. Figure 39 shows the model used for DC signals.

Mixture Density Network (MDN) with Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) Model

Figure 39. Mixture Density Network with Monte Carlo Dropout.

The architecture is as follows:

- **Input:** regular layers (Dense, Conv1D, etc.)
- **ANN Layers:** Any standard stack of hidden layers (dense, convolutional, recurrent, etc.) of the neural network.
- **Mixture heads:** Three parallel dense layers produce:
 - Logit outputs: mixing weights (probability of each Gaussian).
 - Means for each component.
 - Log standard deviations for each component.
- **Output:** For K Gaussians and predicting a single scalar, the model outputs K values for mixing weights, K values for means, and K values for standard deviations.

The loss function is the Negative Log-Likelihood (NLL). For each training point, it computes the likelihood of the true value under the predicted mixture distribution.

6.3.4 Model training procedure

1. Create a dataset with a representative sample of the signals that the system can generate, randomizing the order.

2. Separate target from features.
3. Separate between training (80%) and testing (20%) datasets.
4. Normalize the features using a scaler.
5. Create the model of the neural network (type of neural network, number of layers, number of neurons, dropout rate, activation function, optimizer, loss, metric, batch size, epochs).
6. Train the model with the training dataset.
7. Evaluate the predictions on the testing sets and calculate the metrics.

6.3.5 Bootstrap method for neural network

The fundamental principle behind bootstrapping in neural networks is resampling with replacement the original training dataset to create multiple datasets, called bootstrap samples, and then training separate models on each of these datasets. The variability among the predictions of these models can be used to estimate the uncertainty of the neural network.

The procedure starts by training a neural network model on the entire training dataset to provide a baseline for comparison. Multiple bootstrap samples are generated from this original training dataset by randomly sampling with replacement until a new dataset of the same size as the original is created. Then, each bootstrap sample is used to train separate neural network models, potentially capturing different aspects of the data. The trained models are used to make predictions on the test dataset, which results in multiple sets of predictions for each data point. Finally, the mean and standard deviation of the predictions from the different models for each data point are calculated. The standard deviation of the predictions is used as an estimate of the uncertainty of the model.

The bootstrap method to estimate the uncertainty of a neural network requires training multiple models and generating a high number of predictions. This can be computationally expensive and time-consuming, particularly when dealing with large datasets and complex neural networks. Additionally, training multiple models on slightly different datasets can lead to overfitting if the models are too complex or if the bootstrap samples introduce too much variance, meaning their predictions can vary widely with different training datasets. The bootstrapping process can exacerbate this.

Considering the disadvantages of bootstrapping, the GUM-compliant method Monte Carlo and Monte Carlo Dropout is used to evaluate the uncertainty of the DT, but having the bootstrap method as a backup option.

6.3.6 Uncertainty contribution of relevant parameters

➤ Errors and uncertainties in the model

Different sources of errors and uncertainties in neural networks were investigated and identified in these categories:

- Numerical errors: This results due to floating-point round-off errors from different computation orders in the neural network's calculations. This is dependent on the Python libraries used.
- Epistemic Uncertainty (Model Uncertainty): This arises from the model's limited knowledge of the data and can be reduced by providing more data.
- Aleatoric Uncertainty (Data Uncertainty): Data bias due to lack of information and variability in system parameters. This results from noise inherent in the data and cannot be reduced by adding more data.

The uncertainty will be evaluated using Monte Carlo Dropout, Bayesian, or Ensemble approaches.

➤ **Errors and uncertainties in the instrument**

In the case of measurement instruments, the sources of error and uncertainty are:

- Digitizer voltage measurements with Agilent 3458A, NI PXI5922 and $\Sigma\Delta$ digitizer. The uncertainties are defined in the manuals and from previous characterizations.
- White and power line noise in the system.
- Quantization error from Josephson system resolution: $\pm 72.5 \mu\text{V}$.
- Microwave frequency measurement. This is related to the stability of Cesium and Rubidium clocks and was obtained from a test report of the microwave synthesizer.
- Cryocooler temperature measurements: extracted from calibration certificate, $\pm 4 \text{ mK}$.

The error of the voltage steps will be determined by comparing the predictions of the model with the theoretical voltage of the PJVS signal.

6.3.7 Statistical modelling of the influence factors

Table 10 shows the probability distribution and uncertainty contribution of the selected influence factors.

Table 10. List of influence factors, their probability distribution, and uncertainty contribution.

Influence factor	Symbol	Description	Probability distribution	Uncertainty contribution
Numerical errors	ε_{num}	Floating point round-off errors	Uniform	Type B
ML model uncertainty	σ_{ML}	From calculations	Normal	Combined (type A and B)
Voltage measurement	V_m	From the digitizers	Normal	Combined (type A and B)
Noise components	η	Noise influence on the measurement setup and measured data	Normal	Type A
Quantization error	ε_q	Josephson system resolution	Uniform	Type B
Microwave frequency measurement	f_{mw}	Related to atomic clocks	Normal	Combined (type A and B)
Cryocooler temperature measurement	T_{cc}	From temperature sensor	Normal	Combined (type A and B)

6.3.8 Uncertainty evaluation model simplification

After a sensitivity analysis and considering the impact of each error and

uncertainty source, it was determined that the model sources are more critical than the instrument sources, the epistemic uncertainty being the most predominant. This uncertainty is due to the model's limited knowledge and can be reduced with more data.

The uncertainty of the neural network will be evaluated using the Monte Carlo Dropout method.

MC Dropout is a method used to estimate uncertainties in neural network predictions by interpreting dropout, typically used as a regularization technique, as a form of Bayesian approximation. Dropout randomly deactivates neuron connections during training to prevent overfitting. By keeping dropout active during inference and performing multiple forward passes, the predictions become stochastic, effectively sampling from an approximate posterior distribution over the model's parameters. Figure 40 illustrates the method.

Figure 40. Monte Carlo Dropout method for uncertainty estimation of neural networks.

The procedure to calculate the predictions and their uncertainty is as follows:

1. Keep dropout active during test time (in inference mode).
2. Perform N stochastic forward passes for the same input (typically 100).
3. Collect the N predictions to compute the mean prediction (average the N outputs to get the final prediction), and the uncertainty (variance or standard deviation of the N predictions).

Figure 41 depicts an example of a 1 V DC signal sampled at 20 kHz. The uncertainty can be reduced if the dropout rate is reduced during model training. Tests with a dropout rate of 15%, 10%, and 5% should be performed to compare the results, and assess sensitivity of uncertainty estimation to the dropout rate.

Figure 41. Uncertainty estimation of the model using the Monte Carlo dropout method for an 8-step signal.

The error of the voltage steps is determined by comparing the predictions of the model with the theoretical voltage of the PJVS signal. Results show that the uncertainty is in the order of $10 \mu\text{V/V}$, the same order as the measurements.

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